

RESEARCH: RECENT TRENDS IN TEACHER EDUCATION

Dr. Anjana Bisht

Assistant Professor, Shri Guru Ram Das College of Education, Halwara

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Abstract

Teaching has come a long way, and has become more interactive and experiential for both, teachers, and learners. Hence, the need of the hour is a quality teacher's education programme to streamline, rational and address pedagogical issues. Teacher education courses are very much connected to practice as well as theory (<https://files.eric.ed.gov/>). It cannot be denied that 'quality' of education is a direct consequence and outcome of the quality teacher's education programmes. Good quality teacher-education programme enhances their proficiency & competency to face new challenges in the field of education in today's technology driven scenario.

This paper is an attempt to indicate changes that has incurred in teacher education in India and provide an overview of trends, reforms, and innovations in teacher education programmes. It also discusses the need of innovative practices that can be included in teacher education programmes; not only to facilitates improvement of school education; also committed and professionally well qualified teachers to meet the challenges in rapidly changing technologically driven globalized world.

Key words: trends, teacher education, teaching-learning.

Introduction

Couplet of Sant Kabir "Guru Govind dou khade, kaake laagoon paye Balihari guru aapne, Govind diyo milaye." (I face both God and my guru. Whom should I bow to first? I first bow to my guru because he is the one who showed me the path to God.). Similarly, Chanakya also quoted that "Shikshak kabhi sadharan nahi hota, pralay aur nirman uske god me palte hai." (The teacher could never be ordinary. Both, construction, and destruction, belongs to him.). These lines show how important role teacher plays in educating students. They do not just teach students but influence them for good. The role of a teacher is not limited to only the classroom but their different roles can be seen even outside the classroom. According to NCTE (1998) teacher is the most important element in any

educational program and plays a pivotal role in implementation of educational process at any stage. Though there are various other factors, still level of student's achievement is determined by teachers' competence. There is no denying fact that the quality of education basically depends on the quality of teachers. Teacher education is a continuous process and its pre-service and in-service components are complimentary to each other. Hence, intent efforts are need to improve teacher education programmes, as their practice ensure transformative learning, where both, teacher and learner are co-constructors of knowledge.

Kothari commission has said that, "the destiny of India is being shaped in its classrooms." Today there is paradigm shift from teacher dominated classroom practices to that of partnership between the teacher and the learners and their peers. Now the focus is on having teachers-be futurist leaders to ensure sustainable education. The key role of educational institutions is reflected in a variety of initiatives taken to transform the nature and function of education-both formal as well as non-formal. New expectations of technologically driven society and universal accessibility to quality education has necessitated improvement in the system of teacher education, so as, to prepare professionally trained quality teachers.

Improving Teachers' Skill by Doing Research

In today's technologically driven society, education has become more interactive, experiential, and teaching has gone a long way from the traditional classroom teaching methods. Today, teachers are not just lecturers, but guides; and students are not just listeners, but co-explorers of knowledge (<https://files.eric.ed.gov/>). Thus, to cater the needs of rapid changes in education; teaching skills too have evolved. Though, variety of education-centred skills may sometimes seem overwhelming for a teacher. However, Classroom Action Research (CAR) is one method that can help a teacher to see the aspects of his/her teaching that need improvement. As a result, they can be more effective in teaching and students can gain a much better understanding of those topics.

Classroom Action Research (CAR) is more specific and concerned with current classroom situations. It is a tool not only to find out what the students need but also for teachers to identify what they themselves need to improve in their teaching skills. It is a step towards better teaching, and consequently, a better quality of education.

E-Learning

E-Learning is a relatively new method of learning, one that has become integral to education. Today E-learning has become the new normal and the pandemic has accelerated the roll-out of E-Learning. Today educational institutions are using computers not only for office work;

but for teaching and conducting exams too. It has proven that E-Learning can be as effective as classroom learning when designed properly. Blended learning too has shown better outcomes than classroom learning in many evaluations. The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 also advocates a blended learning route for the future (<https://idronline.org/article/education/>). The number of EdTech platforms has also been growing at a rapid pace. Ministry of Education proposed the National Education Digital Architecture (NDEAR) with a vision to create a national digital infrastructure that energises and catalyses the education ecosystem.

Collaborative Learning

Collaboration is the process of working together to achieve a common goal. In teaching-learning process, the common goal is always better learner outcomes. In collaborative learning teachers collaborate for creating a growth-based learning environment with an objective to increase students learning progress. Collaborative teaching environment provide opportunities for teachers to learn from and with each other on an ongoing basis. Teachers can observe other teachers in action, engage in professional conversations about the impact of different approaches, and get feedback on their own teaching (<https://elearning.tki.org.nz/Teaching/>). Teachers who work together, learn from each other and the educational experiences that are active, social, contextual, engaging, and student-owned lead to deeper learning. In today's society, social media is the most common platform used by learners too for collaborating with each other. They learn more about specific subjects, test out ideas and theories, and gauge each other's opinions etc. If done correctly, it is a great opportunity to break up the monopoly of the lecture, and help learners to become more productive members of society in the future. Hence, collaborative learning should be included in the curriculum-in classroom teaching as well as pre-service and in-service teacher training programmes.

Constructive Learning Theory

Constructivism is a learning theory which holds that learners construct an interpretation based on past experiences, personal views, and socio-cultural background etc. To put it simply, Constructivism is the theory that says learners construct knowledge rather than just passively take in information. The role of teachers is very important within the constructivism learning theory as it is a way of teaching, where knowledge is not just passively transmitted by teachers. Here instead of just telling learners what to believe, teachers encourage them to think and logically construct knowledge themselves. In other words, teachers work as a

facilitator to aid the student to come to their own understanding. In constructive learning theory teachers' responsibility is to create a collaborative problem-solving environment where learners actively participate in their own learning.

Improving Critical Thinking Skills

In today's complex and rapidly changing world, the ability to think critically is very essential. Also, the critical thinking skills are vital to deal with the bombarded information from various sources. Critical thinking is not an inherent ability; instead, it is a learned skill that can be improved through practice and self-reflection. Developing critical thinking skills at a young age can have lifelong benefits. Hence, in the teaching-learning process teachers should consider building critical thinking skills in all the rubrics and lesson plans they use in their classrooms. With little creativity and innovation teachers can develop critical thinking skills in classrooms; no matter what subject they teach. Following strategies can help in improving critical thinking skills among students:

- students often hesitate to ask questions due to fear of teacher, public speaking, or embarrassment etc. thus, encourage them to ask more and more questions.
- due to stage fear or public speaking students don't participate in debates, discussions, plays etc. thus, encouraging them for the same will gradually develop their skill.
- asking them to critically analyse something that they read, watch or do often, but take it for granted.
- activities can be organised to practice how to analyse arguments and identify claims, conclusion, evidences, etc.
- through project works, assignments etc. encourage student creativity by engaging them in productive struggle. Working independently or in groups will develop their skills.

In a constant transforming world, it is important to possess skill to analyse critically and adjust accordingly. By providing congenial environment in classrooms learners can improve their capacity to think critically and make decisions based on evidence and logical thinking. Learners become confident, informed, and empowered individuals, who can successfully navigate the intricacies of the world.

Multicultural Education

Multiculturalism is the process of giving equal justice to all religions, cultures, without any discrimination. Education is a means of cultivating, preserving and transitioning culture.

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Thus, to inculcate multiculturalism in country like India, it is imperative to inculcate multiculturalism in education. Some provisions of the New Education Policy 2020 in relation to multicultural education are very striking. Experts believe that multiculturalism in education is liberal, progressive and prevent the victimization of ethnically diverse groups. Multicultural classrooms dissimilate prejudice that one might have about their ethnically-diverse classmates. In such classrooms, both teachers and students celebrate the diverse culture of India. Though, some teachers are finding it difficult to relate the curriculum and teach the classes, where students are from multicultural background. However, being challenging in preparing and organising daily classroom activities teachers can help students grasp an understanding for the multiculturalism. Multicultural approach in teaching-learning process widens the horizon of learners. Teaching in such classrooms is all about being open to new ideas, and sharing this with students.

Global Education

Today global learning is very essential, as barriers between nations and people continue to fade. Everyone has a role to play in achieving sustainable global development. Also, there is an urgent need of a strong education system. As the huge gaps in quality and equitable education has created learning crisis in global education; which in turn is widening social gaps as well. Hence, global education is the need of hour. As it emphasizes the interconnectedness and diversity of all the world's regions. Also, it is the most effective means of achieving the ambitions of the Agenda, 2030.

Conclusion

On the basis of above discussion following factors can be drawn for successful implementation of new approaches to teacher education;

- **A clear vision of effective teaching** make goals and purpose a reality. It gives directions for prioritisation and resource allocation. Clear vision makes teaching-learning process simpler and more meaningful. By creating a clear vision teachers can adjust, modify, and present a coherent message.
- **2. Integrating theory and practice** may acquire a critical outlook in addressing problems that teachers may encounter in the classroom and develop the capacity to continually review and improve their approaches.
- **3. Highly skilled and well supported supervising teachers**, who are accomplished adult educators as well as expert teachers, equipped to play the pivotal role they are assigned in these programs.

- 4. Though, it cannot be denied that self-motivated and industrious teachers utilise their own capabilities, resources etc. to keep themselves abreast with latest trends and skills. Still, for sustainable and scalable partnership to bring the resources and capabilities of all parties (teachers, students, and stakeholders) on the table is the need of hour. As major focus is on the high-quality education system, therefore, the teacher education programs need be structured and modified; to enables them to respond dynamically to problems and challenges in the field of education.
- Pre-service teacher education programme provides a significant opportunity to improve this component of education. As teachers are the main catalytic agent for introducing desirable changes in the teaching-learning process. Thus, teacher being the pivot of the entire educational system, attempts should be made for motivating them to become innovative and creative.

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